

Psychological And Sociological Reasons Of Suicide

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Summary

Suicide refers to the act of a person intentionally ending their own life, often influenced by psychological and

societal factors, and the rising incidence of such instances is now seen as disturbing. A multitude of research has been undertaken about suicide attempts, which represent a significant societal reality globally. The prevalence of suicide among young individuals may be attributed to their difficulty in resolving issues. Research has identified several elements that contribute to suicide. While suicide instances are seen as individual actions, they are regarded as a phenomena arising from the interplay of societal processes and contexts. The occurrence of suicide attempts among young persons at their most productive life stages presents significant challenges. This research constitutes a segment of institutional inquiry. A discussion was held based on the acquired facts and relevant literature.

Keywords: *Suicide Attempt, Personality Disorder, Mental Problems, Stress, Nervous Breakdown*

INTRODUCTION

It is evident that those who engage in suicide often possess a significant health issue. When assessing suicide occurrences from a comprehensive standpoint, they should be seen as a sociological, psychological, and psychiatric societal phenomena. Individuals who commit suicide often initiate this conduct as a result of the interplay of many circumstances. The significance of religious, economic, social, and cultural influences has been underscored as paramount among these variables. The interrelations among these elements have also been established. Individuals who attempt suicide are often afflicted by depression and poor health. Suicidal behaviors are recognized as a progression that begins with stress and culminates in the erosion of spiritual integrity and the emergence of aberrant behaviors when an individual's circumstances deteriorate. Individuals resort to suicide as an escape when confronted with perilous circumstances, grappling with personal difficulties and unable to identify solutions or other avenues. Dirik, 2009. Individuals at risk are more prone to suicide attempts; hence, meta-analyses indicate that therapeutic interventions significantly contribute to the prevention and reduction of suicides, as shown by the mitigation of such behaviors. The analysis of societal structure and the operation of social norms has informed the endeavors of social researchers and the creators of the Sociology discipline. The growing prominence of structural functionalism has fostered the emergence of many viewpoints and interpretations. According to Durkheim, one of these posits that contemporary civilization has a distinct reality. Certain scholars and scientists have elucidated the causative linkages of suicide as follows: According to psychodramatic theory, Freud attributes the impact of unrestrained rage to the subconscious, Beck emphasizes a

gloomy worldview, and Lestler posits it as a taught response to painful experiences. The variability of suicide as a phenomena among individuals, arising from diverse ideas and motivations, has resulted in the development of several theories. Data from official organizations indicate that suicide incidents are obscured and not accurately represented owing to societal pressures imposed on people. This rate is projected to be between 35% and 45% in 2024. The rise in suicide incidents in recent years has elicited alarm. Notwithstanding the implemented safeguards, suicide attempts, a profound sorrow for mankind, remain unavoidable. Research indicates that studies conducted in our regions scrutinize multiple aspects, including the cultural and material power of society, age and gender distribution, individual behaviors, challenges in emotional expression, pessimism, feelings of loneliness, psychiatric attitudes, and social conditions. The primary objective of these investigations and research is to avert suicide and to comprehend the causal relationships involved.

AIM

This research aims to meticulously examine the evolution of the suicide phenomena by exploring its psychological and social impacts, analyzing contributing causes, and implementing measures to mitigate the issue.

METHOD

This study used a literature review, a qualitative research approach. Qualitative research grounded in literature review possesses numerous advantages and limitations. Qualitative data enables researchers to investigate their subjects more thoroughly, focusing on the causes, patterns, and purposes of actions and occurrences. Qualitative research is shown as an effective methodology for in-depth exploration of human phenomena, particularly those associated with the learning process and its primary participants. This technique offers a rudimentary response without precise quantitative values. This research technique will provide the greatest data about the psychological and social factors of suicide for this study.

FINDINGS

Analysis of societal study data reveals a consistent rise in suicide rates among individuals aged 14 to 25. (Şahin, 2003) While suicide occurs across all age demographics, instances among those under 13 are seen as a significant health crisis. Data from studies conducted by the World Health Organization indicate that approximately 165,000 individuals commit suicide annually in Europe, while around 800,000 individuals are lost to suicide globally. Furthermore, there has been a 70% increase in the suicide rate over the past 50 years. Suicide has both a societal and an individual component. Research indicates that a someone tries suicide every forty seconds globally, with a minimum of 1,000 individuals succumbing to suicide each day. The World Health Organization reports that suicide is among the top ten causes of mortality globally. This statistic fluctuates based on the circumstances of the nations. The most apparent factor contributing to these situations is attributable to cultural and economic causes. Religious beliefs and societal traditions serve as potent ideals that may mitigate instances of suicide. The reality and perception of suicide might differ based on religious, cultural, and societal frameworks. In some societies, people may resort to suicide as an escape from embarrassing activities. In Turkish culture and societal norms, suicide is not accepted. Islam has many hadiths on suicide and the prohibition against it. Incidents of suicide

Research initiatives focused on self-harm prevention have been established and executed since the early 1980s. Research findings indicate that individuals who have painful experiences and are exposed to such suffering are likely to acquire habitual behaviors and enhance their propensity for self-harm. Examining the psychological elements and motivations behind suicidal ideation can enhance our knowledge of the person. The interventions and resistances derived from the studies seek to elucidate the underlying causes and circumstances preceding the suicide attempt. The approach used to regulate and address the factors that precipitate suicidal conduct is termed therapeutic application. A multitude of studies and research have been conducted on the issue. Systematic studies undertaken routinely enable the acquisition of knowledge about the provision of first aid to those who attempt suicide, as well as the many interventions and recommendations that specialists in the area may use to influence the individual via professional application. Research indicates that resilience to challenges is characterized by the resources a person has to thrive throughout adversity. While some statistics indicate that resilience offers a protective benefit to military people, drug abusers, and convicts, the lack of research on specific occupational groups is seen as a barrier and a shortcoming in achieving robust outcomes. This study will illuminate future research by examining the cognitive patterns people construct with the repetitive contemplation of bad memories. Suicide attempts by individuals will be associated with more explicit motivations. The performed investigations will reveal the degree to which an individual's feeling of sociality and belonging to their community influence suicidal behavior. The results indicate a correlation between

people' suicidal ideations and the actualization of fatal acts. An assessment is being carried out about the rates and hazards associated with those impacted by their activities. The degree to which the person who tries suicide contributes to the development of many negative mental health issues is stressed. The scientific comparison of suicide attempts reveals cubic and sophisticated suicide models. In all investigations and research on suicide attempts, societal consensus is that suicide is associated with perversion and obsessive cognition. Sociologists assert that the proliferation of obsession in society is attributable to the commodification of labor due to economic and industrial advancement, the erosion of emotionality by modernity, and the globalization facilitated by urbanization, which restructures relationships and lives in accordance with evolving economic relations. The changes impacting people' lives have resulted in a rise in suicide attempts and impulsive behaviors. Consequently, it is underscored that suicide instances might differ based on the societal phenomena they engender, and that the impacts of such occurrences are transmitted to subsequent generations. In several countries, suicide is deemed unacceptable based on the prevailing moral standards. It is standard practice to investigate suicide situations thoroughly and ethically. We must critically evaluate civilizations that see suicide as a normative and acceptable behavior. Consequently, the assessment of death and suicide attempts must to adhere to ethical principles. Conversely, persisting with a demeanor that jeopardizes economic stability and well-being will be repudiated by society. Society must choose a path of moral compromise in a systematic and coherent manner. The individual begins the understanding of self within the familial framework. The individual's subsequent life phase include educational and professional pursuits. The primary determinants influencing the development of self-concept are the religious and cultural values of the individual's society of origin, which play a crucial role in its construction and evolution. The individual's self-identity is thus formed. The individual's viewpoint on all occurrences evolves with the experiences encountered. A mature society aspires to establish an organized system when people possess a sense of ownership over their environment, maintain solid interpersonal relationships, and when societal values and judgments are reinforced by alternative views. (Fromm, 1993, p. 143) The evolution of superego concepts inside an individual's culture will counteract external pressures and reduce suicide attempts. Suicide attempts are seen differently by everyone. Our perceptions of a person who selflessly gives his life for his nation and one who takes his own life without apparent cause are markedly different. Scientist and researcher Baudrillard highlighted that death occurrences without significance are neither acknowledged nor accepted in contemporary society. The reduction in death sentences is inversely related to the quantity of convicts executed. At this juncture, persons who attempt suicide blame themselves by evaluating the society in which they exist throughout the procedure. Baudrillard, 2008 The realities of life and death fluctuate based on an individual's circumstances on a given day. Individuals possess the awareness that they cannot evade

the inevitability of death, and that all living entities will ultimately confront this occurrence. This is recognized as the exclusive possession of a person. The manner in which he/she intends to nurture this entity and the methods he/she chooses to facilitate its growth will be contingent upon his/her discretion. The link between life and death is experienced and assessed variably by each person. It is crucial that people be not isolated within their community, and that their decisions and actions are guided by their own principles and regulations, while respecting the rights of others. They must recognize that our acts and behaviors are accurately interpreted by others, otherwise they will elicit responses from them. Utilizing this data, we will analyze and address the social determinants of suicide cases and the corresponding sociological perspectives that emerge. The low incidence of suicide in certain societies underscores the necessity of examining the reasons and circumstances that lead individuals to consider this option, as well as the societal rejection associated with this phenomenon. In Japan, a developed and modern society, as well as in other cultures, suicide is regarded as an honorable act. Individuals may take their own lives due to the belief that they have committed a disgraceful act stemming from an irreparable mistake, perceived as shameful both by society and themselves. Consequently, those in society who began to lose their communities at the conclusion of the Second World War chose to end their lives honorably via suicide rather than face imprisonment. This conduct may be seen as a result of their awareness of personal duties, the internalization of self-concept, and the conscious recognition of it as a learnt and esteemed behavior within society. The estrangement of individuals from societal ideals induces distress and may result in suicide attempts (Geçtan, 1994). Durkheim discusses the most prevalent mental diseases and their association with lunacy after his explanation of suicide. This notion posits that lunacy is characterized by distinct behaviors and cognitive patterns, suggesting that abrupt emotional shifts inevitably alter the foundations of mental existence. Durkheim claimed that some mental diseases could not be the impetus for suicidal behavior, asserting that suicide does not constitute a manifestation of insanity. His argument posits that there is no correlation between suicide and mental disorders. The low incidence of suicide attempts in modern cultures is not attributable to a reduced prevalence of mental health conditions within such populations. The decline of people's mental states for numerous causes is not a contributing factor to suicide. Individuals with mental diseases are acknowledged to have a higher propensity for suicide compared to those without such conditions. This highlights the need to examine the known or unknown elements contributing to an individual's propensity for suicide (Durkheim 2014). In many impoverished communities, suicide is occasionally seen as a mandated act prescribed by the gods to preserve the tribe's honor, and the individual who does this act is deemed cursed within the community. In many traditional African communities, where such instances are prevalent, it is thought that a person who commits suicide should not be

physically contacted. It is thought, based on superstition, that touching a someone who has committed suicide would result in the same fate. It is believed that the corpse of an individual who dies by suicide should remain untouched by acquaintances and should be disposed of by an unidentified individual. In some tribes, there exists a practice of bestowing an ox onto an anonymous individual. In another tribe, this concept is interpreted differently, leading to the sacrifice of a sheep to deter a suicidal individual. In East African cultures, it is believed that a person who commits suicide should be cremated together with the tree from which they hung themselves. (Metzger 1969). Numerous beliefs and narratives include legendary occurrences associated with suicide in the historical contexts of cultures with profound legacies. Antigone, the most renowned figure among them, committed suicide, holding significant relevance in Greek mythology. Numerous illustrations depicting suicide exist in Egypt. In Mayan history, the practice and custom of dedicating one's body to the gods is also evident. Among the Mongol peoples, there exists a belief in malevolent spirits known as "Abaz and Alban," which symbolize suicide. In Turkish mythology, "Satılay Hanım" is depicted as the goddess of malevolence. The association of the term with the act of selling fosters the impression of it as a malevolent entity. Satılay Hanım, a malevolent entity associated with mental diseases and suicide, is described as a deceptive spirit that particularly targets vulnerable and despondent persons, inciting them to take their own lives (Sümer 2016). Suicide is an unequivocal phenomenon in all communities. Every suicide incident has distinct characteristics and motivations. The occurrence of suicide occurrences varies based on the phenomenon's genesis, its manifestation, and the societal responses it elicits. Examples of this include prevalent wartime occurrences, the threat of contagious illnesses, and the shift towards societal growth and change. In early times, the prevailing style and attributes of suicide were recognized as actions undertaken to escape issues like as aging, dread of illness, and enduring unrelenting agony. In tribes, when a member acts contrary to societal laws and exhibits shame, it is often anticipated that he will commit himself.

CAUSES OF SUICIDE

Scientists assert that upon investigation and analysis of suicide motivations, societal values emerge as the predominant theme behind suicide instances. Upon investigating and analyzing the grounds for suicide, a comparison is conducted with societal factors based on the acquired data. During this study, individual suicide incidents should be examined. Examining a substantial number of examples independently, in various types and formats, will provide insights on the variety of motivations. This data will elucidate the prevalence of suicide cases

and their causative relationships. Despite Durkheim's assertion in his research that societal elements could not influence individual suicide behaviors, he explicitly refuted these aspects. In light of these research, he aided in clarifying the differentiation of societal influences by altering suicide incidents. The inadequacy of expectations and demands that drive people to engage socially becomes prominent. Insufficiently satisfied expectations and demands disrupt social communication and destroy relationships. Research has shown that the extent to which people engage with one another correlates with the incidence of suicide within certain groups. The individual's age, gender, and religion are crucial factors in the integration process. Metzger 1969 Erving Goffman's thesis is one of the most significant and recognized views on the link between suicide and society. Erwing characterized his thesis as the interaction of people with societal members based on their looks, with the mutual influence of persons harboring bad sentiments. The idea posits that physical defects in persons (such as hearing or visual impairments, or loss of limbs), weak will, emotions, distorted beliefs susceptible to oppression, and character disorders, including moral deficiencies, may serve as causative factors. Disorders such as mental illnesses, incarceration, drug and alcohol addiction, homosexuality as a sexual deviation, variations in sexual orientation, and suicidal behaviors are often stigmatized within society. Stigmas are associated with several elements, including religion, ethnicity, and nationality, which are subjects of social sciences. These stigmas may be inherited via familial lineage and can affect all family members in diverse manners. Stigma is a phenomena when people feel compelled to exist due to their deviation from societal norms. Individuals use strategies such as therapy, surgical intervention, and rehabilitation to mitigate the impact of this stigma. A person devoid of physical imperfections tries to gain acceptance within their culture due to feelings of alienation from their community. Consequently, those who bear a stigma label are unable to lead a life comparable to that of typical folks. Stigmatized persons, who strive for societal acceptance, endeavor to adhere to societal laws and norms. Certain stigmatized people, conversely, choose to end their lives rather than contest these norms. Another researcher, Maurice, analyzed suicide instances attributed to societal factors while assessing Durkheim's work on suicide. Both experts contend that the difficulties people encounter throughout their life serve as a significant catalyst for suicide. Halbwack endeavored to pinpoint the shortcomings of prior research by using the technical advancements of his day. He has directed several researchers in psychopathological research and investigations about persons using this approach. Halbwachs has conducted several known investigations and research, while also critiquing them in some instances. Halbwachs questioned the neglect of selfish and pathological motivations for suicide in Durkheim's examination of suicide cases, deeming it a significant shortcoming. He contended that hypnosis may be used to identify alterations in the awareness of those who attempted suicide. Despite the similarities between his work and

Durkheim's, he faced significant criticism and had disagreements with Durkheim in many areas. Primarily, there are disputes on the dependability of the statistical data findings. Studies examining suicide statistics across nations highlight that the findings of this data may fluctuate and should remain confidential. He challenged the significance of differentiating living circumstances between urban and rural locations. He discusses the significance of the distinction between people' living environments and situations, as well as the relevant influencing elements, according to the theory he advocates. Halbwachs said that a key critique he directed at Durkheim's research and ideas was the need of considering particular family structures alongside the notion of religion, seeing this an essential problem. Halbwachs asserts the need of establishing an extensive field of research focused specifically on religious matters. Halbwachs conducted a thorough and meticulous examination of suicide cases in both rural and urban settings. He meticulously examined Durkheim's research and theories on suicide instances and included the sociological distinctions among the cases with illustrations. He examined and validated Durkheim's claim that suicides increase in correlation with economic hardships and crises, attributing this causation to the disparity in work prospects between modern societies and rural villages. In these processes, the severity of depression escalates concurrently with a rise in suicide intentions. Halbwachs posits that, in contrast to Durkheim's classifications, there may also exist straightforward suicides. Normal suicides stem from an inability to create good communication and social interactions, influenced by many psychological and societal circumstances. Elements such as professional setbacks, unreciprocated affection, and persistent illnesses may contribute to suicide. The progression of suicides exhibits distinct variations. Research indicates that a primary factor contributing to pathological suicides is societal isolation, namely detachment from the community. Durkheim's assertion that "suicide is a social phenomenon" validated the sociological perspective (Giddens 1965). Another scholar, Jacques Peuchet, has authored several books and memoirs on this topic. Upon meticulous examination of these memoirs, Karl Maxx concludes that the repressive and conservative dispositions of contemporary affluent individuals foster a patriarchal family framework that mostly subjugates youth and women. Karl contends that the limitation of personal freedom and the attitudes and demands put on people are primary contributors to the incidence of suicide. Oppressive families and authorities who employ coercion inflict violence on those under their care, display unjust behaviors, impose mobbing tactics and punitive measures, leading individuals with sensitive, fragile, anxious, and agitated dispositions to be more prone to suicidal attempts in such circumstances. In Marx's examination of people' private lives, beyond political or economic concerns, the primary focus is the oppression and brutality inflicted upon women in a society that marginalizes the individual. Maxx asserts that women are seen as subservient and are subjugated by men who view them as possessions, driven by envy. Starting from the perspective of women as people, Marx, who addresses repressive attitudes rooted in the structures of developed societies, also offered

significant criticism of this phenomenon.

Marx posits that suicide is but one of many manifestations of the pervasive social conduct shown by warriors, stemming from their ennui in the presence of those consistently driven to engage in novel activities. Marx and Peuchet demonstrate that economic issues contribute to suicide, with poor salaries, poverty, rising unemployment, and economic injustice significantly impacting people's lives. This is succinctly highlighted as a problem resulting from societal injustice. According to the analyses of Henry-Short, Marx, and Goffman about suicide episodes, a crucial aspect is the correlation between an individual's societal position and status and the occurrence of such instances. Fractures are evident in people who struggle to adjust to the changes occurring in our nation. Individuals who lack the sensitivity to engage cohesively with their society and those who struggle with socialization are more likely to feel fractures and may be inclined to attempt suicide. Durkheim's theory of suicide is highly regarded due to its opinions and analyses, which are unequivocally valid. The incidence of suicide among cultures and the contributing variables are influenced by the values, habits, and traditions inherent to such communities. Rapid global events are altering our cultural customs. Consequently, the incidence of suicide cases and the primary motivations for suicide are evolving. The rise in variability has led to the conclusion that anomic suicides are now the most prevalent kind of suicide. In the contemporary world, transformations are happening at an unparalleled velocity, resulting in several anomalies. Significant change has occurred in the 21st century, and the issue of globalization is arising. While this process has political, financial, and economic components, the cultural dimension, which holds more significance than these variables, is paramount. The quick evolution of cultural values due to globalization and the selection of strategic direction are shown by the use and swift advancement of information and technology. This evolution has resulted in a communication issue that hinders people from effectively connecting with one another in society. Advancements in technology enable individuals to engage with diverse lives and cultures of unfamiliar people, facilitating communication and interaction with strangers. This kind of communication will effectively influence the transformation of society values and norms via individual interactions. The consequences and transformations induced by global development on people originate with the family, the fundamental unit of the person, and manifest in aspects such as social status, gender preferences and perceptions, and professional life. These alterations adversely impact people's self-concepts and induce their evolution. These abrupt and obligatory alterations disturb the psychological condition of humans with multifaceted and diverse aspects. The prevalence of capitalist ideology in the present world has led to the creation of new psychological diseases in humans. The alterations in individuals typically encompass stress induced by professional life, depressive disorders, maladaptive responses to rapid societal changes, personality disorders, substance abuse, alcohol dependency, schizophrenic behaviors, and mental health issues stemming from shifts in sexual orientation.

The self-inflicted damage people do during abrupt transitions may adversely affect not just themselves but also the fundamental ideals deemed significant in society. The identity of the one executing this action and the one inflicting pain against himself is not a societal issue, but rather pertains to all moral and value considerations. Anomic suicide events are prevalent in our culture, reflecting both individual emotional analysis and societal value neglect.

PSYCHOLOGICAL EFFECTS

Freud posits that our two primary instincts influence and activate the psyche. He underscored that one of them is the sexual drive and the other is the violent instinct. Freud posits that the phenomena of suicide is instigated by the aggressive urge, leading the person to direct this impulse inward and engage in the deed. If a person merges the fury he generates with thoughts of death, it will ultimately lead to a suicide attempt after the culmination of his activities (Fromm, 1996). Karl Menninger thinks that Freud's concept should be broadened and seen as a triadic occurrence. He posits that an individual's fundamental urge to murder stems from a want to be killed, which should be seen as a manifestation of fury and hatred. Furthermore, he contends that the desire to die is the third component, asserting that death instincts are triggered, leading to the occurrence of suicidal phenomena. Individuals who experience a decline in self-confidence and motivation may withdraw inwardly, opting for introversion. Rather than comprehending and addressing their circumstances, they may resort to the path of least resistance, abandoning logical reasoning and contemplating suicide. Due to the rise in psychological factors contributing to suicide, there has been a 40% increase in instances over the last decade. It has been shown that 85% of suicide instances are attributable to those experiencing depression. The onset of depression in people is precipitated by heightened pessimism, a lack of problem-solving abilities, impaired cognitive functioning, and an inability to use rational and logical thinking skills. Individuals may replace their erroneous thought processes with resentment, wrath, a desire for retribution, and antagonism towards others. In instances of suicide, which are prevalent among people, it is believed that the suicidal impulse may arise from the perception that the surviving family members would bear responsibility for the individual's death. Suicide is a fundamental subject that psychologists and psychiatrists have rigorously studied in the current century. In analyzing these situations, they see suicide as the individual's own duty and issue. They have acknowledged the facts and circumstances in our society about this subject, emphasizing the significance of these aspects and the need of addressing them as a critical concern. In these assessments, our specialists mostly used a sociological viewpoint, scrutinizing the psychological frameworks of persons and the complexities of the issues they encountered, in

pursuit of solutions to their inquiries. They recognized that the perspectives presented in this regard have several deficiencies. Notwithstanding these deficiencies, they achieved significant progress in their research and contributed to the understanding of suicide reasons. While psychologists and psychiatrists collaborate on joint studies, a definitive distinction between their fields remains elusive. These disciplines are interrelated, and integrating their perspectives under a unified scientific framework will yield more expedient results and enhance comprehension. This discourse will examine the psychiatric viewpoint, followed by a comparative analysis based on the evidence provided by psychology. The perspectives and assessments of psychiatrists about suicide instances and facts are notably intriguing. For an extended period, the approach to addressing the suicide issue included diagnosing any mental disorder. They concluded that people engaged in suicide unknowingly due to the influence of mental disease behavior. Psychiatrists, guided by this evidence, often addressed the issue inside mental institutions by supposing a mental disorder was present in every instance of suicide. Nonetheless, the data acquired unequivocally demonstrated that there was no association between insanity and suicidal inclinations, and that they significantly differed in terms of frequency. It is inappropriate to classify the actions of certain mentally ill individuals who inadvertently end their lives as suicide. There exists a significant distinction between the suicide attempt rates of individuals exhibiting typical behavior and those of individuals suffering from mental and psychological disorders. Psychiatry continues to address this problem in the same manner. An individual who commits suicide is often categorized under one of the following conditions: personality disorders, psychosis, depressive psychological disorders, or panic attack psychosis. These elements may indeed influence an individual's suicide attempt. The significance of these diseases in shaping the individual's personality structure, together with the influence of familial and societal norms within their immediate context, cannot be overlooked. When these statistics are considered, they will significantly elucidate the reasons a person may resort to suicide. Bourdine, a French psychiatrist, thinks that suicide is a pathological occurrence. Esquirol, a French psychiatrist, thinks that a person who commits suicide does so during a significant mental crisis. The perception of suicide as a kind of lunacy hindered the acceptance of this hypothesis for an extended period. Subsequently, the scientist Delmas, who analyzed suicide cases from a psychopathological perspective, dismissed the proposed sociological theories and contended that the critical aspect of suicide cases lies in the individual's desire to die and the resolution of his/her will, which are entirely manifestations of personal determinism. He contends that the person elects death of their own will. He asserts that the underlying causes of suicide may be categorized into three distinct factors. These represent

1. Individual's melancholic periods
2. Chronic depression and the maintenance of this condition by the individual
3. Excessive excitement due to the nature of the individual
4. He asserts that 93% of suicides result from persistent mental depression or depression stemming from the individual's constitution. Initially, Delmas, who sought to explain suicide from a psychological standpoint, ascribed episodes of suicide to the individual's constitution. A significant number of scholars rejected Delmas' idea and examined it seriously. Theories that focus on suicide and associated phenomena within psychology are termed psychoanalytic theories. Freud, the proponent of these views, contends that suicide eludes comprehensive explanation and definitive characterization. Freud and his adherents did several investigations based on this idea to demonstrate that psychological states are a contributing factor to an individual's susceptibility to suicide. Freud's primary focus of study is violence. He attempted to elucidate the dynamics of suicide episodes by analyzing the mental states of depression in persons and contended that personality has three levels. The id is the fundamental component in the development of personality. It is a term including the whole of a psychological latent strength that comprises the instincts inherited from one's lineage. Consequently, the surplus energy stored in the individual's body will be discharged, resulting in tension inside the organism. The ego is regarded as the paramount component of psychological phenomena. Subsequent to childhood, it diverges from the id's definition and progressively evolves, aiding in the development of the individual's personality. The component that governs people's interactions with the external environment is referred to as the ego.

The superego is defined as the embodiment of values instilled via the reward and punishment system conveyed by the child's parents. In typical persons, these three fundamental aspects function consistently and without interruption, also serving to reconcile disputes inside the individual's internal realm. When inner conflict develops unconsciously and uncontrollably, the ego becomes incapacitated, leading to neurosis. During perilous situations, the person enters a state of self-defense. Upon acknowledging the imminent threat, he promptly initiates an escape plan; but, if flight proves unfeasible and no alternative exists, he may choose for self-termination as a means to alleviate his suffering. In the presence of such perils, the person, akin to all living organisms, need to safeguard oneself or evade the hazardous circumstance. Freud faced criticism from several adherents for emphasizing the instinctual aspects of suicide cases. Freud's biological perspective on suicide faced criticism for its inadequacy regarding the sociological dimensions of the person, despite the fact that a key trait that differentiates humans from other organisms is their psychosocial nature. A notable researcher in this field is the renowned psychoanalyst Karl Menninger, who advocated for Freud in his analyses. Menninger primarily endeavored to elucidate the intricacies of Freud's fundamental concepts. Menninger posits that the inclination to murder diminishes with age, but the urge to die increases. Suicide rates among the younger age are rising owing to relational issues. He said that actual suicide instances rise among the elderly, reiterating that older folks often choose death to avoid further suffering.

Adler posited that suicide is a distinct social issue that arises when a person lacks social interest. He said that the decline in societal engagement among people is a prevalent factor in the occurrence of failures. The individual's indulgence is a contributing factor to suicidal tendencies, since they may resort to suicide even under challenging circumstances, experiencing a sense of helplessness. Jung defines suicide episodes as deliberate or inadvertent actions, whether active or passive, intended to garner societal attention from the individual's community. All studies have focused on a certain aspect of an individual's

personality, expressing curiosity in the consequences on other dimensions, although mostly concentrating on personality itself. Individuals exist inside a society that imposes regulations on their status and expected conduct. Consequently, students must recognize that perspectives that overlook social variables will not provide a healthy outcome and that some study undertaken will undoubtedly be inadequate. Research on persons who have recently died by suicide indicates that many indicated in their narratives of suicide attempts that their actions were motivated by the negative experiences inflicted upon them by others. Hopelessness in people emerges from the depletion of their capacity to combat the challenges they encounter. Moreover, persons with psychological and mental issues related to balance and personality do not engage in suicidal behavior.

SOCIOLOGICAL IMPACTS

While we have concentrated on the reasons of suicide in the previously addressed issues, sociology also has significant relevance in the study of suicide. The significance of social aspects cannot be overstated among the paramount considerations. The social structure, with the physical environment, may regulate individual behavior. Typically, a person contemplating suicide will display conduct that contradicts their inherent character. The suicide rate is significantly elevated in adverse and detrimental societies compared to healthy civilizations. The rationale for this is that the individual's resilience to adverse circumstances is equivalent to that of others. Sociologists contend that the inadequate regulation of society over people influences suicidal behavior. Numerous sociological ideas have been shaped and substantiated by Durkheim's concepts. Durkheim undertook several investigations into the causes and determinants of suicide, with his statistical analyses being the first use of statistical techniques in sociology. Statistical analyses indicate that suicide rates in certain civilizations have remained unchanged over the last decade. Consequently, the factors contributing to suicide must be acknowledged, both for individual and societal reasons. In his analysis of suicide episodes, Durkheim sought to establish the connection between suicide occurrences and people by focusing on non-social factors rather than social ones. In his study, he endeavored to elucidate his findings by juxtaposing psychological, biological, and physical environmental components with non-social variables and statistical rates. His idea posits that mental disease, alcohol addiction, and race are unrelated to suicide. Despite a larger prevalence of mental illness among women, suicide rates are elevated among males. This phenomenon is also seen among racial disparities. Despite elevated incidences of mental illness among Jews, their suicide rates remain notably low. This is because suicide is deemed abnormal according to their beliefs and is not sanctioned by their faith. The impact of certain climatic movements on suicide incidents has also been examined. The seasonal rise in suicide incidents and the higher prevalence of such occurrences during the day compared to night are believed to be attributable to a more vigorous and busy social life. Durkheim asserts that

although there is no direct correlation between elements unrelated to social phenomena and suicides, he highlights that these factors have an indirect influence on suicide rates. He asserts that people lack protection from the religion, politics, community, and family to which they belong. In other words, it transpires when a person experiences loneliness inside a society due to weak social bonds with their affiliated organizations. As the connections people form with their respective groups diminish, their allegiance to the perceived community also declines. The individual experiences loneliness due to solitude in their own domains and the concerns that captivate their attention. He asserts that life diminishes in vibrancy and significance due to the emotions elicited by this solitude. Membership in society is the fundamental need for an individual's existence. Durkheim's study demonstrated this idea via statistical data, asserting that in all industrialized civilizations, single persons have higher suicide rates than married individuals, while childless individuals have greater suicide rates than those with children. Another perspective posits that a person commits suicide not due to isolation from their group, but rather due to an overwhelming attachment to it. The most notable instance of this is the Hindus. A woman's desire to be cremated at her husband's funeral in India exemplifies this. This is seen as an activity undertaken by the person to satisfy a social obligation. The person who neglects this societal commitment is aware that he will lead a disreputable life and face repercussions from the community to which he belongs. Societal pressure and attitudes towards people contribute to the promotion of suicide attempts. The interaction hypothesis posits that an individual's engagement with others in society is deemed significant. This individual's action engenders sentiments of personal pride, sorrow, and humiliation. The social structure surrounding an individual perpetually exerts control over them; adherence to social norms results in acceptance, appreciation, and support from members of their community. Conversely, if the conduct is contradictory, it is repudiated and not embraced by society and the persons around him. He contends that the person may be compelled to commit suicide in response to this circumstance. In field theory, the propensity for people to attempt suicide is influenced by their environmental context. He contends that the individual regulates his conduct based on societal responses. Douglas, a researcher, refutes Durkheim's thesis via a comparative investigation of suicide. Douglas contends that no theory should rely on statistical data and asserts that the formulation of sociological theories is detrimental. He elucidates that in the act of suicide, the person inflicts self-punishment and seeks to terminate his existence. Conversely, Ginsberg has seen anomie as a psychological issue rather than a reality. Gibbs posits that the incidence of suicide within a society is inversely proportionate to the degree of unity in goals and objectives; hence, a greater level of unification correlates with a reduced number of suicide instances. Durkheim also tailored his investigations according to the findings derived from this study. The correlation between societal problems and suicide in some industrialized civilizations is a crucial element for elucidating perspectives that may significantly contribute to

analogous hypotheses. The traditions, religions, practices, and values of certain nations significantly influence suicide attempts. Communication deficiencies among people have emerged as a prevalent issue, impacting both economic and industrial progress, and often serve as a catalyst for suicide incidents. In contemporary industrialized civilizations, the suicide rate among urban residents exceeds that of persons residing in traditional rural settings. In summary, a comparison of emerging nations reveals that suicide rates are elevated in rural regions compared to developed areas, particularly in the context of technical and industrial advancement. Individuals relocating from rural regions to developed urban areas may resort to suicide owing to the challenges and adaption issues arising from their altered cultural milieu. Individuals used to living in a foreign nation have numerous challenges and adaptation issues when returning to their homeland, which represent a distinct manifestation of the same difficulties. Individuals are seen to attempt suicide as a result of cultural difficulties. Research indicates that the suicide rates among persons moving from one nation to another are lower than those of the host country. While unplanned and uneven urbanization, technological advancement, industrialization, and migration contribute to rising suicide rates, issues may manifest differently when cultural distinctions among communities diminish or vanish entirely. A reduction in the incidence of suicide attempts among males is seen during wartime, when social engagement and communal solidarity are heightened. When people unite for a shared objective and engage in the exchange of ideas, they find it simpler to set aside their personal issues. In light of the evolving scenario, rather than people articulating their sentiments of animosity, social integration ensues.

CONCLUSION

The primary focus of sociology is the inquiry of how society may exist. Durkheim asserted that the notion of society could only be safeguarded via the establishment and adherence to a set of social regulations. The preservation and maintenance of the overall social order may be achieved via fundamental social structures and institutions in people's lives. Certain institutions, like politics, family, and educational systems, are at the forefront of these entities. Durkheim asserts that when these institutions inadequately perform their functions, the resulting anomie adversely impacts people and undermines their connections to society. Durkheim asserts that suicide is entirely a sociological phenomena, contending that acts of suicide result from dysfunctions within fundamental social structures. He said that people's endeavors to engage socially are shown not just via cultural comparison and hybridization via the media, but also through the accelerating phenomenon of migration. He said that a significant issue arising from migration is economic difficulty, which therefore leads to a rise in persons' happiness with this circumstance.

Factors that adversely impact persons' lives diminish their quality of life and foster pessimism. Depression, the most prevalent affliction of contemporary society, is increasingly integrating into people's lives, beyond the conventional concept of a sickness. These factors are seen as directly impacting an individual's quality of life and contributing to suicidal tendencies. This finding indicates that the elements that precipitate and cause suicide episodes have been identified and conclusions have been drawn accordingly. Suicide incidents reflect an escalation in the disparities resulting from an individual's accelerated lifestyle throughout the shift from traditional to contemporary societal structures. Economic factors are a primary contributor to suicides. Challenges encountered during cultural transitions contribute to a rise in suicide rates. Conversely, calamities and conflicts result in a reduction in suicides. Alcohol and drug use are other contributing factors to suicide. Recently, heightened competitiveness in the workplace and educational settings has escalated stress levels, hence increasing the risk of suicide. The isolation, labeling, and stigmatization of people within their community, along with the heightened risk of suicide among those with differing ideas and religions. The encroachment of technology into personal privacy and the degradation of societal conditions contribute significantly to elevated suicide risks, primarily via the exacerbation of individual shame. Although deaths are inevitable and often abrupt, suicide is a preventable and anticipated occurrence. Consequently, the determinants of suicide must consistently be monitored, and suitable measures should be implemented. The economic and social framework influences suicide attempts. It often presents considerable dangers for young persons.

RESTRAINT

This study is constrained by prior scientific research undertaken globally. While the literature evaluation was performed within the existing framework, it is crucial to acknowledge that various geographical locations and cultural settings were not evaluated from a comprehensive standpoint. Nonetheless, due to the particular technique used and the temporal limits of this research, it may possess concerns for generalizability.

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